

MMZ

Figure 4E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4E

Lane 1: Sib-2 Clone-1, **Lane 2: I-ASD-2 Clone 1**, **Lane 3: Sib-2 Clone 2**, Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Clone 2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4E: GAPDH for PS6 film

Figure 4E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4E

Lane 1: Sib-2 Clone-1, Lane 2: **I-ASD-2 Clone 1**, Lane 3: **Sib-2 Clone 2**, Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Clone 2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4E

Lane 1: Sib-2 Clone-1, **Lane 2: I-ASD-2 Clone 1**, **Lane 3: Sib-2 Clone 2**, Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Clone 2

total
S6 7122

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4E: GAPDH for Total S6 film

Crab
GAPDH

✓
Good

Figure 4E Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4E

Lane 1: Sib-2 Clone-1, Lane 2: I-ASD-2 Clone 1, Lane 3: Sib-2 Clone 2, Lane 4: I-ASD-2 Clone 2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows